

D6.3 Dissemination activities and materials including practice abstracts

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Dissemination activities and materials

This document follows the update of the plan for Dissemination and Exploitation drawn in the Deliverable 6.2 submitted in February 2024 and provides an overall review of all dissemination activities and materials organised or produced from the beginning of the project until August 2025. As outlined in the Grant Agreement, this deliverable also includes the first batch of the practice abstracts, which will get extended in D6.4 in month 48 of the project. This deliverable serves as a progress report on dissemination task.

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Type of deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data management plan	<input type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	<input type="checkbox"/>

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1. Introduction

As part of the Work Package 6, dissemination activities help to ensure the maximum visibility of the project's activities, while considering the accessibility and impact of the latter. The dissemination activities seek to make the outcomes of the project visible but also accessible to the different target groups identified in the strategic documents.

The dissemination goals and methodology were developed in close collaboration with WP6 and Communication Leader FEUGA and developed in a comprehensive manner with the exploitation task. It thus aims at transferring the project results to their intended users through diverse channels and tools carefully selected.

The method through which stakeholders are targeted and engaged was defined and updated in Deliverable 6.1 and 6.2. The activities described aim to maximise opportunities for the exploitation of project results at different decision-making scales (local, regional, national and European).

Based on the plan for the dissemination and exploitation, activities were implemented throughout the duration of the project and by all partners. This document will serve as a report taking stock of dissemination implementation of the RUSTIK project.

Furthermore, this deliverable includes the first batch of seven practice abstracts.

1.1. Objectives of the Work Package

Dissemination activities are part of the Work Package 6, as well as communication activities. This work package focuses on planning and executing communication activities to promote the RUSTIK project, and to disseminate the results to a wide audience, as well as to define the exploitation strategy of the project. It has thus developed tools and frameworks for effective implementation, capacity building, peer exchange and monitoring tools to stimulate engagement among partners.

As stated in the communication and dissemination plan D6.2, WP6 objectives are:

- To maximise the impact of RUSTIK with an overall strategy of communication, dissemination, and exploitation.
- To disseminate, promote, and connect the project results and facilitate the dialogue with stakeholders and participation in existing European networks.
- To link RUSTIK with existing networks, projects, and initiatives to promote an effective and efficient transfer of knowledge, gathering a wide set of relevant stakeholders.
- To develop an exploitation plan to promote replicability, long-term use, and transferability of results.

1.2. EC rights and obligations related to results

Dissemination of the project's result is a contractual obligation for projects funded under Horizon Europe. Partners, as beneficiaries, must conduct various activities through different means including electronic tools and printed materials such as project websites, publications, leaflets, press releases, posters, as well as conferences, meetings and workshops at different levels. While trying to target a wide audience, dissemination activities shall be compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality obligations and the legitimate interests of the owner(s) of the results, as stated in the EU Grant Agreement.

In all dissemination and communication materials, the recognition of the EU's contribution must be mentioned, and the EU emblem displayed with appropriate prominence. Each work package and partner has been complying with this rule consistently in every communication and dissemination material and event about the project.

1.3. Target groups

Both dissemination and communication activities are meant to deliver the right and understandable information to the right audience, at the best format and best timing.

Within the plan for the dissemination and exploitation, target groups have been identified and are listed below:

- **Policy and Programme designers and implementers**: This group spans from the European Union (EU) to national and rural levels, and encompasses public bodies, policymakers, and regional development agencies. This diverse group serves as a primary focus for the project, as they play a pivotal role in formulating, refining, and executing policies and programmes. The project aims to establish a meaningful connection with these stakeholders to ensure that the research outcomes and achievements catalyse tangible changes in policies at local, regional, and national tiers. Effective engagement with this multifaceted audience is crucial for the project's success in influencing policy development and implementation across different administrative levels.
- **Academia & Scientific community**: Universities and other organisations working with rural research and spatial planning. Reaching those organisations is important for exchanging knowledge and experience among peers and for enriching the research activities of the RUSTIK project.
- **Rural Inhabitants**: This group includes all individuals or organizations that are impacted by the project, such as inhabitants of the Pilot Regions rural areas (elderly, youth, rural businesses and entrepreneurs, farmers, etc.). They constitute a key target audience for which the project results are tailored, given their significance in providing valuable inputs and feedback to the project.
- **Civil society organisations**: This group includes a variety of entities, rural community organizations and non-profit, with an intersectoral approach which might also provide inputs to the project, and which can raise awareness about our project activities at local level.
- **Industry and services**: This group includes other individuals, companies operating in rural areas and institutions such as rural clusters and cooperatives engaged with territorial and

- rural development. This target group involves different value chains such as health, tourism, agriculture, waste management, transport, etc..
- **General public:** Awareness raising on the project topics, particularly concerning the improvement of economic prospects and quality of life in rural areas through sustainable (social, economic, and environmental) transitions. Demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges, highlighting the relevance of these solutions in rural and unpopulated areas.
 - **Media professionals:** Including journalists, editors, and outlets at local, national, and international levels, are an essential audience for the project. The goal is to share findings through media channels, boosting public awareness. This collaboration ensures broader outreach, contributes to informed discourse, and aligns with the project's key objectives of impact and outreach.

In addition, specific target audiences for each cluster of living lab have been identified. Please refer to D6.2 for more details.

2. Dissemination implementation

Dissemination activities were implemented through the different channels the project developed as part of communication tasks: the website, social media channels, newsletter, press releases, videos, leaflets, posters, etc.

The RUSTIK consortium actively shared project insights across a variety of European and national platforms. Presentations were delivered at major events such as the LEADER Congress, Euromontana's Annual Conference and General Assembly, as well as several webinars hosted by the Rural Pact Support Office. At the national level, findings were also featured during annual events organized by three project partners.

To support collaboration and knowledge exchange, Euromontana developed a dynamic networking database in Excel. This living document tracks both past and ongoing projects related to RUSTIK's themes and includes a dedicated section on upcoming events relevant to consortium partners. It is regularly updated by Euromontana, with new opportunities and developments shared via targeted emails, Jour Fixe meetings, and a designated Teams channel within the project's shared workspace. Oversight of the consortium's broader networking efforts is provided by IfLS.

This collaborative approach enabled RUSTIK partners to present project findings at both scientific and practitioner-oriented events, including the Regional Studies Association Winter Conference, the European Society for Rural Sociology Conference, the LEADER Congress, and Euromontana's General Assembly.

Additionally, to enhance the visibility and accessibility of project outcomes, Euromontana produced summary articles highlighting key deliverables. These focused on topics such as rural functional areas and rural proofing and were tailored to meet the needs of both academic researchers and local practitioners engaged in testing or applying these concepts.

To explore how RUSTIK aligns with broader European rural policy objectives, consortium partners held discussions on the project's connection to initiatives under the Long-Term Vision for Rural

Areas (LTVRA). These conversations highlighted uncertainties around the terminology and scope of the LTVRA, prompting a need for clarification.

In response, Euromontana developed a clear and accessible factsheet along with a survey aimed at assessing how RUSTIK’s Living Labs (LL) contribute to LTVRA goals. The objective was twofold: to map out the concrete contributions of the Living Labs to these high-level European strategies, and to help the LL Pilot Regions themselves better recognize their impact at the European level.

Survey results were shared during a monthly Living Labs meeting, fostering greater awareness and dialogue among participants. A dedicated article summarizing the findings has also been drafted and is currently under review for publication.

Additionally, Euromontana has been actively tracking relevant events where real-world applications of the LTVRA are discussed, with the aim of encouraging participation from Living Labs and ensuring their work is represented in these European policy conversations.

Below is a table summarising the different dissemination activities the project had undergone:

Type of dissemination activities
<p>Conferences (event, date, place, partners involved)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation on ‘Designing data experiments for challenge-oriented innovation in rural areas: Methodology and practice reflections’, Regional Studies Association Winter Conference, 10/11/2023, UK (London), CCRI • Conference of deliverable 1.1 at a conference on ‘Territories in transition after the crises: an international comparison’, Italy (Pavia), 30/11/2023, CREA • Panel on ‘Transdisciplinarity: Presentation on RUSTIK Living Lab Approach’, European Society for Rural Sociology, 05/07/2023, France (Rennes), IfLS • Presentation on ‘Conceptualising Functional Rural Areas: Policy Directions and Research Foundations’, Regional Studies Association Annual Conference, Ljubljana (Slovenia), 16/06/2023, IfLS. • Presentation on RUSTIK approach and first outcomes of Living Lab at Deutscher Kongress für Geographie (German Geographer’s Congress), Frankfurt (Germany) 21/09/2023, IfLS. • Demonstration of the GIS platform on the way of local food to representatives of tourism sector at the 7th annual conference Smarttourism.bg, organised under the patronage of the Ministry of tourism, 11/2024, Uni Sofia • 27th FEBA Annual conference Transforming Futures: Sustainability, Innovation and governance. 22/11/2024, Uni Sofia • Participation in the Third edition of the Agro Academy Innovations in the agribusiness, 17-19/03/2025, Uni Sofia • Regional Studies Association Annual Conference, Faculty of Economics, University of Porto, Portugal, 6-9/05/2025; CREA • European Congress on Renewal and Rural Development, Poznań, Poland, Session “Strengthening rural communities on the way to sustainable transformation” 8-10/05/2025, Institute of Geography and Spatial Organization, university of Ljubljana • RUSTIK regional workshop North Karelia, Finland, 05/06/2025

- Rural proofing: looking at policies through the rural lens, session on “putting rural proofing into practice”, online, 12/06/2025, MCRIT
- European Society of Rural Sociology, session on “reflecting on inclusive research practices in rural contexts”, Latvia, Riga, CCRI, IfLS,
- XVII EAAE Congress: Food System Transformation in Challenging Times, session on “CAP strategic planning”, 28/08/2025, planned, Germany, Bonn, IfLS, UL
- 64th ERSAs Athens Congress: Regional Science in Turbulent Times. In search of a resilient, sustainable and inclusive future. Potential joint session with GRANULAR on “taking into account diversity to shape just rural futures: novel indicators for resilient and inclusive development” – contribution to be confirmed.
- EUGO Congress: the role of knowledge in shaping sustainable development of rural areas in the local and regional dimension, session “the relevance of diverse information collection in research on transition of rural areas”, planned 10/09/2025, Vienna, Austria, various Living Labs contributions
- IMC 2025 International Mountain Conference session 3.196 “mountain diversities for shared innovative solutions: the role of SMEs for sustainable and resilient development in mountain rural areas” planned 14-18/09/2025; Innsbruck, Austria, BAB
- Second Rural Pact Conference: from vision to action: empowering rural areas for the future. 15-17/09/2025, Courtrai, Belgium, Information corner, Euromontana, ELARD.
 - XXI European Rural Development Network Conference on food systems transition for sustainable rural development, planned 23-24/09/2025, Bucharest, Romania. Poster presentation.

Collaboration with EU funded projects

- Presentation on Deliverable 1.1 in a webinar on rural functional areas together with sister project GRANULAR, 23/02/2024, online, CREA
- Presentation in a webinar on the methodology in the RUSTIK Austrian Living Lab with sister project GRANULAR, 27/11/2023, online, BAB
- Workshop on rural proofing at Euromontana’s General Assembly, 22/11/2023, Belgium (Brussels), CREA
- Presentation about/in a Living Lab event (Gloucestershire data day), 26/04/2023, UK (Gloucestershire), GRCC
- Panel discussion in a national event (NICRE's State of Rural Enterprise National Event), 23/11/2023, UK (London), GRCC
- Participation in a GRANULAR webinar on “Living labs in rural areas: how to?”, online, 27/11/2023, BAB
- Participation at an EU webinar (RPSO Good practice webinar on rural areas tackling climate change), 20/03/2024, online, UEF, online, 28/02/2024, CREA
- Presentation at partner event (GRCC centenary event) on RUSTIK’s digital work, 20/07/2023, UK (Gloucestershire), GRCC
- Presentation in the GRANULAR project’s webinar on functional areas
- Presentation in the webinar of GRANULAR on Living Labs: driving change in rural areas 18/03/2025, online, Ersilia Foundation and EMD Sant Miquel de Balenyà
- Second regional dissemination workshop. planned 09/10/2025. Sober, Spain. Collaboration with GRANULAR and Down to earth projects.

- European Week of Regions and Cities, session on rural proofing and data-earth observation. In collaboration with GRANULAR and VALORADA projects. planned 14/10/2025. UEF, CREA, FEUGA, Euromontana.

Table 1: Dissemination activities overview

Deliverable and KPI	Objective	Format	Indicative timing	Status
3 policy briefs	To share the project results with non expert audiences, in particular policy makers at all levels	5-10 pages publications, to describe project concepts, with examples from the Living Labs	M30: 1st Policy Brief M36: 2nd Policy Brief M48: Final Policy Brief as part of D6.4	x
10 practice abstracts	Short summaries describing the main information/recommendation/practice that can be used by the end-users in their daily practice	EIP Practice Abstract to be uploaded on the EU CAP Network portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M36: First batch of practice abstracts in D6.3 (development of the outlines) • M48: Second batch of practice abstracts in D6.4 (revised and validated) 	First batch done
Practice Guide	To sum up the key messages to trigger transitions in rural communities as evidenced from other WPs	Guide with case studies and analyses. Translated in at least in 4 languages	Target: M45	x
14 Testimonial Videos	Showcase and disseminate challenges and lessons learnt from the work carried out in Living Labs	To be decided with Living Labs	Dependent on progress in Living Labs M20-M24: Definition of content and scope of each video M24-M30: Production M31-M48: Dissemination	Ongoing

Mid-term dissemination event with members of the European Parliament	To deliver mid term/preliminary results and recommendations to policymakers	Joint webinar with sister project envisaged	Event to take place after M28	Done
14 dissemination leaflets	To disseminate LLs results and lessons learned with non-expert audiences.	Leaflet format of the project (3 pages folded)	Start the elaboration of the content at the end of cycle 2 for LLs.	Ongoing

Table 2: Dissemination materials KPIs and status

2.1. Focus: Mid term event - the role of data in driving transitions in rural areas

On 30 April 2025, the RUSTIK project hosted a webinar titled “The role of data in driving transitions in rural areas”, to share the main results of the project with the prism of data for the Mid Term event.

Rural regions provide vital ecosystem services, high-quality land-based products, and cultural value, yet they are grappling with demographic shifts, climate change pressures, digital divides, and limited economic diversification. In response, RUSTIK speakers’ presentations showed how RUSTIK leverages data to guide rural areas toward sustainable, place-based transitions, identifying their unique functions, challenges, and potentials to inform smarter policies and interventions.

The webinar convened experts, project partners, and regional representatives. It explored critical themes such as:

- Data access and protection,
- Integrating data into local decision-making,
- Real-world insights from Living Labs conducted in the RUSTIK Pilot Regions, and
- Hands-on experience with the RUSTIK Data Viewer tool

The agenda of the webinar is available here: [RUSTIK MIDTERM Agenda](#).

Screenshot 1 of the webinar

Attendees engaged in interactive workshops, navigating the Data Viewer to explore layers of indicators and spatial data, and discussed how structured data can drive meaningful rural transitions.

Key Takeaways & Significance

- **Data as a foundational asset:** The webinar reinforced the importance of data in mapping out rural dynamics and shaping sustainable futures. Areas such as resilience, diversity, and transitions across socio-economic, environmental, and digital dimensions hinge on high-quality, localized data.
- **Data Viewer spotlight:** Participants received guided exposure to the Data Viewer, the project's online tool enabling exploration of data layers from the European core to 14 LL Pilot Regions featuring mapping.
- **Collaborative governance emphasis:** The event encouraged integrating data into policymaking, stressing issues such as data availability, standardization, and stakeholder engagement to support place-based governance.

Screenshot 2 of the webinar

The recording of the webinar is available on the project website and has been widespread on the social media channels of RUSTIK: <https://rustik-he.eu/2025/04/save-the-date-the-role-of-data-in-driving-transitions-in-rural-areas-rustik-webinar/>

The webinar was attended by 41 participants, including the speakers, and included various profile from other European funded projects, researcher as well as policy makers (mainly from the European Commission).

2.2. Focus: first regional dissemination workshop: innovative responses to rural demographic shifts

As part of the task 6.2, the first regional dissemination workshop was organised on June 5th, 2025. Gathered around the theme of demographic change and innovative responses to it, three LL Pilot Regions from Rhein-Hunsrück (Germany), North Karelia (Finland), and Monmouthshire

(UK) came together to present and exchange ideas on shared challenges in the heart of Koli National Park, Finland.

First regional dissemination workshop in Koli National Park, Finland

This event aimed to disseminate the results developed within these real-life laboratories of the project and trigger peer-to-peer discussions.

Simo Rautiainen, a doctoral researcher at the University of Eastern Finland and the Karelian Institute, set the scene by introducing the host region North Karelia and outlining its demographic challenges over the period 1980 to 2024.

These three Living Labs, regional innovation hubs that experiment with real-world solutions to rural issues, then presented their unique, locally adapted approaches to addressing demographic specificities. Despite the geographical distance, many common patterns emerged.

Svea Thietje and Achim Kistner, both working within the Rhein-Hunsrück Living Lab, presented ongoing initiatives aimed at strengthening the region's demographic resilience. They highlighted two key challenges: out-migration among young people aged 18 to 25, and the gap between supply and demand in the training and apprenticeship market.

Their Living Lab's approach to addressing these challenges involved analysing mismatches in the apprenticeship landscape and improving alignment through a series of actions: organizing focus groups, co-designing surveys, and conducting surveys among young people and regional employers and conducting interviews with multipliers (including agencies, job centres, and local administrations).

They shared the following key achievements:

1. Created a well-founded database on the needs and obstacles faced by both young people and employers in relation to apprenticeships and vocational training.
2. Ensured that young people's voices were heard and considered in discussions around training.
3. Created new networks and revived old ones, fostering dialogue among stakeholders.

4. Attracted political attention – both at the district and regional levels – and initiated discussions with policymakers based on the findings.

In North Karelia, Aura Liski, Project Manager at the Regional Council of North Karelia, presented a survey aimed at collecting data on the integration of immigrants in the region. The data is intended to help municipalities improve their integration services and better support the successful settlement of immigrants, given that the latest reform of the 2025 Integration Act, which made municipalities responsible for promoting the integration of immigrants, lacked the tools and data to evaluate and develop their integration services.

The survey was developed and launched in spring 2024 and has since been expanded to other municipalities in the region. An improved version of the survey is currently being prepared through a multidisciplinary collaboration with regional stakeholders.

Finally, Demelza Jones, Research Fellow at the University of Gloucestershire and representative of the Monmouthshire Living Lab, highlighted how a survey incorporating emotion-based questions on belonging and aspirations, combined with geo-referenced data and secondary datasets, enabled deeper insights and allowed for meaningful local-level comparisons.

In the context of Monmouthshire, which is marked by an ageing population as well as challenges related to housing, employment, and transport, this experimental approach provided valuable understanding of the needs and expectations of younger residents in the region.

Beyond the sharing of achievements, successes, and challenges, the panel discussions also revealed a strong desire to continue these initiatives beyond the timeframe of the project, as some of the results have proven to be valuable tools in themselves for other stakeholders.

2.3. Publications

RUSTIK results will be included in more than 10 scientific publications in open access, peer-reviewed journals. These publications will be presented in scientific conferences.

KPI	Objective	Format	Indicative timing
Min 10 scientific publications; 1 publication/year in sector-specific magazines; Min 5 conference contributions	Disclose RUSTIK deliverables and results via scientific channels and tools	Scientific publications on peer-reviewed and non-scientific magazines. Attending scientific conferences	Starting from M15 when key deliverables start being submitted

Table 3: Summary of the publications KPIs

To reach this objective, a publication tracking tool has been developed, and guidelines and contacts of the consortium members to whom the draft should be submitted are enclosed in the tracker.

Below is a summary of the planned publication towards the end of the project:

Type of publication	Tentative title and content	Planned date / status	Author(s)
Article Review of agricultural economics – Firenze University Press	Italian of The governance of transitions in agri-food systems evidence from the processing tomato supply chains in Spain and Italy	Published April 15, 2024: https://zenodo.org/records/13693938	Francesco Mantino, Barbara Forcina
Article in Journal European Planning Studies	in On inducing innovation in endogenous rural development: A living lab experiment	Published, 24 July https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09654313.2025.2533945	Ewa Korcelli-Olejniczak & Karolina Witeska-Chmielewska.
Article in a journal	Lessons on rural proofing	Unknown	WP2
Other	The RUSTIK database	2026 towards end of the project (final database)	WP2
Article in a journal	Data requirements for facilitating transitions in the EU's regions	To be confirmed	WP2
Chapter in a book	Lessons learnt from LLs	2026 towards end of the project (final database)	
Article in Journal	Methodological article on LLs in rural development - based on evaluation results	2026 towards end of project	WP3
Chapter in a book	Smart comparison on LLs working on CC	2025 – after data experiment is concluded	WP3
Article in Journal	Stimulating transitions	2026 towards end of project	WP5

Article in Journal	Facilitating change through transdisciplinary research	2026 towards end of project	Several partners
Chapter in a book	Capacities and capabilities of rural actors	2026 - towards end of project	IfLS
Article in journal	Induced Innovation in Endogenous Rural Development	2026 - towards end of project	IGSO PAS, FDPA
TBC	Linking research activities and outcomes to European strategies and policies for rural areas. Potentials and challenges based on RUSTIK work	2026 - towards end of project	IfLS

Table 4: Summary of the publication and planned publications

In parallel, efforts have been made to publish a joint special edition in collaboration with the project GRANULAR, and is in progress. In this booklet, RUSTIK would be in charge of the one highlighted in yellow below:

Proposed Papers

1. **Capturing Rural Diversity for better governance of common transitions through place-based strategies**
Authors: Berchoux T., Rac I., Sterly S.
2. **Conceptualizing rural diversity: a framework for understanding multifunctionality**
Authors: Oostindje H., Bock B.
3. **(Re)defining rurality: methodological choices and policy implications in typology design**
Authors: Damari Y., Stjernberg M., Tapia C., Berchoux T.
4. **Testing functional rural area methodology on two different Pilot Regions: how FRA can provide appropriate pictures of mountain areas and highly developed areas**
Authors: Mantino F.
5. **Functional diversity of rural areas in Poland and the effectiveness of regional policy – an approach based on the Functional Rural Areas (FRA) typology**
Authors: Zarębski P., Kurdyś-Kujawska A., Chmieliński P., Wieliczko B.
6. **Valorisation of the tourism potential in the Świętokrzyskie region in the context of the division into Functional Rural Areas**
Authors: Mazur M., Bański J., Korcelli-Olejniczak E., Kamińska W.
7. **A systematic review of novel datasets for developing new indicators of sustainable rural development**
Authors: McCallum I., Hoffer M., Kull M., Berchoux T.
8. **Bridging research and rural realities through Living Labs: from challenges to strategies**
Authors: Stortini F., Marovelli B., Trinchetti T., Berchoux T., Moretti M.
9. **Combining different types of data to model the contribution of excess food distribution to the wellbeing of marginal social groups**
Authors: Soklič M., Erjavec E., Puh L., Rac I.
10. **Bridging Data Gaps: The Use of Innovative Tools in Mapping Short Food Supply Chains in the Tourism Sector**
Authors: Bogdanov N., Todorović S.
11. **Co-creative validation of new social and health data sources in rural areas to improve policy-making aimed at categorising rural areas according to their risk of social exclusion. The case of a Spanish Living Lab.**
Authors: Doyal-Ruiz M.I., Martins-Bodaj B.
12. **Diversity of food systems and their transitions in Europe: implications for policy**
Authors: Chahid N., Berchoux T., Prospero P.
13. **Assessment of the potential of local food supply networks for the development of a regional food brand as a new territorial asset: data experiment evidence from two restaurants in Bulgaria**
Authors: Slavova P., Ivanov G.
14. **Mapping local food producers to identify policy directions for supporting and developing short food supply chains in Poland**
Authors: Kurdyś-Kujawska A., Kloskowski D., Wieliczko B., Floriańczyk Z.
15. **A review of rural proofing methods and their applicability at the local level**
Authors: Mantino F., Miller D., Forcina B., Kahila P., Halme J., Vironen H., Fonseca L.

Figure 1: Proposal for a joint paper with GRANULAR

3. Practice abstracts (PA)

As part of dissemination activities, ten practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI format will be produced in English. Aiming to increase the dissemination of RUSTIK outcomes, a practice abstract is a short summary for practitioners. These practice abstracts are part of the key performance indicators to show that the project has targeted rural communities, EU networks and rural businesses & services.

These abstracts aim to stimulate knowledge exchange and spread innovative solutions across the EU, and are part of the European Innovation Partnership for agricultural productivity and sustainability (EIP-AGRI).

Eventually, the ten practice abstracts will be combined in a practice guide to steer transition for rural communities, which will be translated into at least four languages. The guide might also include the testimonial videos if the subjects are coherent and if there is added value in displaying them together.

As for the process, the topics of the practice abstracts and partners participation were decided on a voluntary basis in Joensuu in June during the project meeting, as part of the WP6 presentation. As lead partner, Euromontana developed guidelines in the following months to guide partners in developing PAs. It includes definitions, examples, advice in writing such abstracts: who they are intended for, size, tone, aim, etc, as well as deadlines.

Figure 2: Graph parts of the guidelines for writing the practice abstracts and sent to respective partners

The table below summarises the topics decided as end-user-friendly and their respective authors. If the first batch of practice abstracts are available below and part of this deliverable, they are also uploaded to the EU CAP Network webpage.

Practice abstracts	Author(s)
Land Use Agent-Based Model	Marite Guevara (Ersilia Foundation) & Andreu Blanch (Entitat Municipal Descentralitzada Sant Miquel de Balenya)
Geographical Identification System: On the Way of Local Food in Troyan, Apriltsi and Ugarchin	Petya Slavova (Sofia University)
Involving Youth in Project Development and Data Collection	Svea Thietje (IfLS) and Achim Kistner (Regionalrat Wirtschaft Rhein-Hunsrück)
Participatory mapping for place-based policymaking in rural areas	Demelza Jones (Countryside and Community Research Institute, University of Gloucestershire and Monmouthshire County Council) & Aimee Morse (Countryside and Community Research Institute, University of Gloucestershire)
Visualizing local food networks: use of Maptionnaire in supporting Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)	Natalija Bogdanov (Faculty of Agriculture – University of Belgrade)
Smart Dashboard: Empowering Data-Driven Decisions for Rural Communities	Mohammad Chizari, Katarina Kubinakova, Daniel Keech (University of Gloucestershire)
Web and data scraping	Chiara Ippoliti, Oriol Biosca, Andreu Ulied (MCRIT)

Table 5: List of the first batch of EIP AGRI practice abstracts

Below are the seven practice abstracts, forming together the first batch of practice abstracts. They will then be uploaded in the EU CAP network website, under RUSTIK page and practice abstracts library.

3.1. PA 1: Land Use Agent-Based Model

The Land Use Agent-Based Model is a forecasting and exploratory tool developed within the RUSTIK project to support local planners and decision-makers. Rather than offering deterministic predictions, the model enables users to explore possible patterns and dynamics of land-use change under different assumptions and constraints.

The core purpose of the model is to inspire and guide local-level planning by simulating the complex interactions between different types of land use: primarily residential, industrial, agricultural, and forest areas. It allows users to observe how residential and industrial expansion may lead to the reduction of agricultural land and forests, under various spatial, economic, and regulatory scenarios.

Land-use change is simulated through a stochastic, path-dependent algorithm that reflects both the unpredictability of real-world development and the emergence of structural patterns over time. Users can explore how initial conditions, such as the number of households, industrial units, or farms, as well as boundary conditions like planning regulations and maximum land capacity, shape future development. The model also integrates interdependencies between land uses, agglomeration effects, and spatial diseconomies, providing a nuanced representation of territorial dynamics.

Developed entirely in Microsoft Excel, the model is designed to be fully transparent and userfriendly. Users can input their own data, adjust model parameters, and even reprogram the algorithm to fit local realities. Its non-linear, stochastic nature allows for flexible experimentation while offering valuable insights into long-term land-use planning.

More Information can be found in chapter 5 of the following RUSTIK report: [Report on data bases development](#).

Authors: Marite Guevara & Andreu Blanch

3.2. PA 2: Geographical Identification System (GIS): On the Way of Local Food in Troyan, Apriltsi and Ugarchin

The GIS 'On the way of Local Food in Troyan, Apriltsi and Ugarchin' is the first map of its kind in Europe that allows to geolocate agri-food actors and to get insight into food at the level of individual settlements and municipalities.

It was developed in response to a gap in Bulgarian public policy, namely the lack of connectivity and knowledge regarding agri-food actors in a territory: who they are, what they produce, where they are located, and what their capacity is.

The platform features ten thematic maps highlighting various agri-food actors such as restaurants, accommodations, organic producers, beekeepers, livestock farms, local food shops, slaughterhouses, distilleries, municipal markets, food festivals, and food-focused vocational schools. It also includes a map of all beneficiaries of the Local Development Strategy led by the Local Action Group Troyan, Apriltsi, Ugarchin. Each entry is described using standardized indicators, including location, types of food produced, and animals raised.

Another map is under development to present specific local products, making them more recognisable and accessible.

Local producers may provide additional information, accessible in the platform.

The system uses publicly available data from official Bulgarian registers. Its innovation lies in connecting this data to reveal insights on potential business partnerships and access to local food.

It creates an opportunity to generate a new type of spatial data usable for business and policy decision-making purposes.

Data are updated once a year, at the beginning of each calendar year.

During the 7th National Conference 'Good Food', organised under the patronage of the Ministry of Agriculture and Food to mark World Food Day, the platform was awarded for digital innovation in the field of local food and tourism.

The platform is available in Bulgarian and English: <https://gis.migta.eu/en/>

Author: Petya Slavova

3.3. PA 3: Involving Youth in Project Development and Data Collection

When a project focuses on young people, it is essential to include them in shaping it. In the RUSTIK case, their participation was crucial for two reasons: we could not understand their needs without their input, and local involvement fosters ownership and increases chances of lasting impact.

From the start, we learned how important clarity is. Young people need to know what they can influence and what is already fixed. If this is unclear, expectations quickly become unrealistic and lead to frustration. Teenagers bring energy and creativity, but they also need guidance to stay within what is feasible. Balancing openness with clear boundaries proved essential.

To reach a broad group, we worked closely with schools. Teachers were invaluable: they distributed our survey link and even gave students time in class to complete it, which resulted in a strong response rate. At the same time, we realised that schools alone risk missing those less engaged or marginalised groups. To reach them, we cooperated with trusted intermediaries (youth workers, local organisations, and employers) and invested time in building trust through transparency and privacy on data use.

Engagement methods also mattered. Workshops and focus groups were most successful when they included practical elements and treated young people as equal partners. For surveys, clear and simple language was key. A pre-test of the questionnaire with a small group of young people helped us spot issues early.

Finally, involving youth requires early planning for permissions, strict data protection rules, and strategies to avoid reaching only the “usual suspects.” It takes extra effort, but the results are worth it: deeper engagement, better insights, and solutions that truly fit their reality.

Authors: Svea Thietje and Achim Kistner

3.4. PA 4: Participatory mapping for place-based policymaking in rural areas

Engaging with younger-working-aged people (aged 16-44) is a challenge for rural local authorities, as they do not regularly use council-run support services. Capturing information at the local level on factors which may encourage this age group to live in the county can also be difficult.

To address this, a survey to capture residents' views on the county was created in Maptionnaire, a platform for the design and management of map-based community engagement. The survey was co-designed with stakeholders across the county to ensure it captured relevant data. It was shared at public engagement events with residents aged 16-44.

This approach increased engagement with a cohort that has historically been under-engaged and improved understanding of residents' views of the county, and key areas for improvement. The survey also generated georeferenced data which allows for targeted interventions to improve residents' quality of life. This data can be combined with secondary data to explore how people's experiences vary by income, household type and other demographic data.

Co-designing the survey with stakeholders ensures the data collected is relevant to a range of audiences. Carefully consider the best questions to capture the data and ensure the final version of the survey takes no longer than 10-minutes to complete.

It is also advisable to engage potential participants in-person, then share the online survey QR code with them following this.

For those without internet access, you can hold workshops which include pinning comments to a physical map. Ongoing engagement with local authority stakeholders was also important to share findings and ensure the data remained accessible.

Authors: Demelza Jones & Aimee Morse

3.5. PA 5: Visualizing local food networks: use of Maptionnaire in supporting Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)

By strengthening ties between local producers and consumers, Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) contribute to more resilient and self-reliant rural economies. They reduce intermediaries, keep

more value in local communities, and promote environmentally friendly practices by minimising transport and encouraging local sourcing. When linked to tourism, they bring additional benefits by enhancing the visitor experience and creating new market opportunities for producers.

The Maptionnaire platform was used to identify and map SFSC participants serving restaurants and guesthouses in the pilot region. It also provided insights into their satisfaction with the collaboration and highlighted the challenges they face. Unlike standard surveys, this tool enables the spatial visualisation of SFSC actors, their classification (farmers, processors, hospitality providers), and their interconnections by product group (e.g. vegetables, meat, dairy), offering a clear picture of the supply chain's structure and relationships.

For SFSC actors, it highlights potential partners, unmet demands, and opportunities for collaboration and market expansion. Understanding the geographical distribution of suppliers and buyers also supports more efficient logistics and targeted business strategies. For municipalities, the tool provides a solid foundation for evidence-based planning, helping them to identify priority areas for support (e.g. infrastructure, policy incentives, investment in cooperatives), and design more effective rural development policies.

The survey can be accessed here: <https://app.maptionnaire.com/p/8ih32yv8tw9>).

Author: Natalija Bogdanov

3.6. PA 6: Smart Dashboard: Empowering Data-Driven Decisions for Rural Communities

The Smart Dashboard is a custom-built, innovative digital tool designed to empower practitioners to process, analyse, and visualize data without needing a background in data science. Developed by the University of Gloucestershire, it ensures full control over its functionality, scalability, and security, providing a robust platform for data-driven decisions.

Its core functionality is delivered through a wizard-based interface that guides users step-by-step. Users can import CSV or Excel datasets or explore datasets available on-line. The platform is built with a focus on security, employing a unique access key for registration and implementing advanced tracking to block brute-force attempts during both registration and login. The main outcomes of the tool are its powerful analysis and visualization features.

The Smart Dashboard allows Cross-Reference Analysis, enabling users to explore complex relationships between multiple datasets at a single geographical level. It also includes an intuitive Heatmap Visualization feature that uses the latest UK geo-boundaries to display data distribution, with normalized values represented by a colour gradient for numerical and a dynamic legend for categorical data.

The geographical coverage can be broadened to other countries, enhancing its use and widening its potential beneficiaries.

The main practical recommendation is to use the Smart Dashboard as a comprehensive yet simple tool for uncovering valuable geographical insights. Its most significant added value is the use of AI to generate text-based summaries and full reports of the analyses. This ensures that even complex findings, including figures and tables, are presented in an easy-to-understand format, directly supporting entrepreneurial activity and informed decision-making in rural areas.

The dashboard is currently in a prototype phase and is not publicly accessible yet.

Authors: Mohammad Chizari, Katarina Kubinakova, Daniel Keech

3.7. PA 7: Web and Data scraping

Web and data scraping refers to the automated extraction of information from websites, digital platforms, and online registries. These techniques allow users to gather large volumes of geolocated and structured data from sources such as OpenStreetMap, Google Maps, or public databases, often in real time and at a relatively low cost.

In local and rural contexts, where official data sources are often fragmented, outdated, or lacking in detail, web scraping offers a practical solution to fill information gaps. It enables the collection of valuable data on infrastructure, services, businesses, mobility, food supply chains, and socioeconomic dynamics, many of which are not covered by traditional statistics. Combined with official datasets and local inputs, scraped data supports the creation of customized indicators and interactive tools, such as dashboards, spatial maps, or decision-support systems.

The approach is easily replicable, scalable, and adaptable to different territorial contexts. It strengthens the capacity of local actors to access relevant data and supports more informed, place-based planning and policy design. However, to ensure responsible use, particular attention must be paid to data quality, interoperability, privacy regulations (e.g. GDPR), and licensing issues. Validation procedures and clear documentation are key to guaranteeing transparency and ethical standards.

Used consciously, web and data scraping can play a strategic role in expanding data availability and enhancing evidence-based policymaking for sustainable territorial development.

Authors: Chiara Ippoliti, Oriol Biosca, Andreu Ulied

4. Next steps

The practice abstracts will be completed by at least four others planned for M48 of the project, in order to include the main and latest development of the project. All of them will be included in the practice guide which will summarise the key messages and recommendations to trigger transitions in rural areas, using inputs from the project WPs. It will present several short case studies regarding functional rural areas, improved strategies and governance approaches, that the practice abstracts will support.

In addition to this guide, translated into at least 4 languages, 14 testimonial videos are in the making with the Pilot Regions partners. A practical guideline for the recording is in preparation to help partners having a homogeneous understanding in the expectation (structure, duration, tips for the recording). They will be in the native languages, with English subtitles. Euromontana will then take care of the editing in collaboration with the Living Labs communications lead and using Canva for the videos created by FEUGA using RUSTIK visuals. In parallel, leaflets about the Living Labs experience will be developed.

Dissemination activities will also be fed by the WP5 work on policy recommendation. RUSTIK will produce three policy briefs that will serve as a vehicle for providing evidence-based policy advice to make informed decisions. More specifically, the policy briefs will target policymakers at the EU, national, regional, and local levels. To facilitate the dissemination and the uptake of results, the policy briefs will be translated into the languages of the pilot regions: German, Spanish, Italian, Polish, Slovenian, English, Finnish, Bulgarian and Serbian. The policy briefs will be disseminated during European, national, regional, and local events. Such key themes as rural proofing, rural functional areas and rural data collection and aggregation could be tackled through these policy briefs.

